

ISic0986

I.Sicily inscription 0986

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 37

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140464

1. □ α □ ω
2. τοίμβος²⁶τύμβος²⁶ Σα-
3. βίνου· ἐν αὐτῷ
4. κῆτε Αὐξάνων
5. ὁ τούτου υἱὸς
6. βιώσας ἔτη κε'.
7. ²palma²
- 8.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492613
EDCS 39102140
PHI 140464

Bibliography

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Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 4.9466

Ferrua, A 1989. Note e giunte alle iscrizioni cristiane antiche della Sicilia. Vatican. At no.481

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